

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 9: Facilitating the usage

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Abstract

This tutorial overviews the new update to JECDM that intends to facilitate the usage of its several components, primarily instantiating the plots and evolutionary algorithms.

Keywords: JECDM, facilitating usage, visualization, evolutionary computation

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1. Introduction

Source package: `t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage`

This tutorial introduces a few minor updates to JECDM that primarily intend to facilitate the usage of its selected components:

- Visualization module: Several factory-like classes dedicated to quickly instantiating `DisplayRangesManager.Params` containers and plots of various types are introduced.
- Evolutionary computation module: Convenient means of constructing custom implementations of the `IEvaluate`, `IReproduce`, and `IConstruct` interfaces are added. They allow for the concise creation of their instances using lambda expressions.

This update includes three sub-tutorials briefly discussed in what follows. Note that the classes introduced in this update are not considered complete and may be extended in the future.

2. Constructing plots using factory-like classes

Source package: `t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots`

This tutorial introduces a few factory-like classes assisting in concise plot creation. These are:

- `Visualization.plot.Plot2DFactory`,
- `Visualization.plot.Plot3DFactory`,
- `Visualization.plot.PCP2DFactory` (parallel coordinates plot),
- `Visualization.plot.Heatmap2DFactory`,
- `Visualization.plot.Heatmap3DFactory`,
- and an auxiliary `drmanager.DRMPFactory` for constructing display ranges manager params containers.

These classes provide various static methods for creating plots of desired types. The construction process may be moderately customized by passing instances of three auxiliary interfaces (adjusters):

1. `plot.ISchemeAdjuster`,
2. `plot.IPlotParamsAdjuster`,
3. `plot.IPostPlotCreationAdjuster`.

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These are one-method interfaces, meaning they can be concisely passed as construction methods arguments (implemented as optional parameters). The adjustments are made after the default parameterizations are applied to the methods. The order of their execution is as provided above. Precisely, the plot scheme can be adjusted first. Then, the plot params container can be adjusted. Finally, the plot may be adjusted after it is created but before it is returned.

In what follows, example usages of the introduced classes are provided. Note that this tutorial document does not provide an overview of all the methods available in these classes. It is left to the Reader to get acquainted with them. The methods used in this tutorial create (by default) plots that have transparent backgrounds, use Times New Roman fonts, and use decimal formatting for the axes (tick labels). What is more, the tutorials are concerned with plot creation only. Thus, no data sets are supplied to the plots. Hence, renders provided in this tutorial portray empty plots. Note that these classes are expected to be extended in the future.

2.1. Creating 2D plots

Source package:
t1.t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots.t1_plot2D

Tutorial1a. This tutorial showcases how to employ *Plot2DFactory* to quickly instantiate a simple 2D plot. Its code is brought in Listing 1 for convenience. The invoked method, by default, sets the plot scheme as imposed by *WhiteScheme* class, sets a transparent background (the plot, not its drawing area), axes' tick labels are set to use decimal formatting, and the fonts of text-related components are set to Times New Roman. Next, the method additionally allows for setting the axes' labels (*f1* and *f2*), the display ranges of both dimensions (fixed [0, 1] intervals), and recalling the font size of all text-related components (1.5, increase by 50%). The expected final render is depicted in Figure 1. Note that the plot background is dark gray, as imposed by the default coloring of the swing *JPanel*. Nevertheless, the drawn render indeed has a transparent background, and one may request, e.g., a screenshot creation to successfully store it in the PNG format.

Listing 1: Instantiating a 2D plot (Tutorial1a)

```
// Creates a simple 2D plot:
// - sets X-axis label to "f1"
// - sets Y-axis label to "f2"
// - sets X and Y-axes limits to [0, 1]
// - rescales the font size of text-related
  components by 1.5 (increased by 50%)
// Important note: the method makes the
  background transparent, sets the font of
  text-related components to Times
// New Roman (by default), sets the axes
  tick labels formatting to decimal, and
  instantiates the scheme as white.
Plot2D plot2D = Plot2DFactory.getPlot("f1",
  "f2", 1.0d, 1.5f);
```

```
Frame frame = new Frame(plot2D, 0.5f); //
  create the frame
// if not called, the axes label will not
  be displayed until some data sets are
  supplied
plot2D.getModel().
  notifyDisplayRangesChangedListeners();
// displays the plot:
frame.setVisible(true);
```


Figure 1: Expected visualization product (Plot 2D; Tutorial1a)

Tutorial1b. This tutorial is a continuation of *Tutorial1a*. It showcases how the plot creation can be further parameterized. Apart from employing a method with more inputs, it also allows processing customization by passing instances of the *ISchemeAdjuster* and *IPlotContainerAdjuster* interfaces. The tutorial's source code is in Listing 2 for convenience. Note that the "adjusters" are passed as two last arguments as lambda expressions. Their inputs are the objects to be adjusted:

1. The first one customizes the plot scheme. First, it sets its background color to white. Then, it adjusts the right and top margins that dictate the distance between the ends of the drawing area and the plot boundaries.
2. Next, the plot container adjuster sets the plot title.

Note that the *Plot2DFactory* class also provides methods that allow plot post adjustment (passing implementation of *IPostPlotCreationAdjuster*). The expected final render of this tutorial is presented in Figure 2.

Listing 2: Instantiating a 2D plot (Tutorial1b)

```
// Creates a simple 2D plot.
```

```

// Important note: the method makes the
// background transparent, sets the font of
// text-related components to Times
// New Roman (by default), sets the axes
// tick labels formatting to decimal, and
// instantiates the scheme as white.

5 Plot2D plot2D = Plot2DFactory.getPlot(
    "f1", //sets X-axis label to "f1"
    "f2", //sets Y-axis label to "f2"
    DRMPFactory.getFor2D(1.0f, 2.0d), // sets
    display ranges as fixed at [0, 1],
    [0, 2] intervals
    5, // sets the number of X-axis ticks to
    5
10 10, // sets the number of Y-axis ticks to
    10
    "0.0", // formatting pattern for the X-
    axis tick labels
    "0.00", // formatting pattern for the Y-
    axis tick labels
    1.5f, // rescales the font size of text-
    related components by 1.5 (increased
    by 50%)
15 scheme -> {
    // Adjusts the scheme object created by
    the method:
    // - sets the plot background color to
    white
    // - adjusts the right and top margins
    // Note that the scheme customizations
    are applied after the default
    adjustments are done
    scheme._colors.put(ColorFields.
    PLOT_BACKGROUND, Color.WHITE);
20 scheme._sizes.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER
    , 0.05f);
    scheme._sizes.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_TOP_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER ,
    0.1f);
    }, pP -> {
    // Adjusts the plot params container
    created by the method:
    // - sets the plot title as provided
    // Note that the plot params container
    customizations are applied after the
    default adjustments are done
25 pP._title = "Example title";
    });

Frame frame = new Frame(plot2D, 0.5f); //
    create the frame
30 // if not called, the axes label will not
    be displayed until some data sets are
    supplied
    plot2D.getModel().
    notifyDisplayRangesChangedListeners();
    // displays the plot:
    frame.setVisible(true);

```


Figure 2: Expected visualization product (Plot 2D; Tutorial1b)

2.2. Creating 3D plots

Source package:

t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots.t2_plot3D

This tutorial follows a similar structurization to the already discussed tutorial on creating 2D plots (Section 2). Further, they are similar to each other to a large extent. Thus, the source codes are not presented or examined here for conciseness. The expected renders are, however, illustrated in Figure 3 (Tutorial2a) and Figure 4 (Tutorial2b).

2.3. Creating 2D parallel coordinates plots

Source package:

t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots.t3_pcp2d

This tutorial follows a similar structurization to the already discussed tutorial on creating 2D plots (Section 2). Further, they are similar to each other to a large extent. Thus, the source codes are not presented or examined here for conciseness. The expected renders are, however, illustrated in Figure 5 (Tutorial3a) and Figure 6 (Tutorial3b).

2.4. Creating 2D heatmaps

Source package:

t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots.t3_heatmap2d

This tutorial follows a similar structurization to the already discussed tutorial on creating 2D plots (Section 2). Further, they are similar to each other to a large extent. Thus, the source

Figure 3: Expected visualization product (Plot 3D; Tutorial2a)

Figure 5: Expected visualization product (PCP 2D; Tutorial3a)

Figure 4: Expected visualization product (Plot 3D; Tutorial2b)

Figure 6: Expected visualization product (PCP 3D; Tutorial3b)

codes are not presented or examined here for conciseness. The expected renders are, however, illustrated in Figure 7 (Tutorial4a) and Figure 4 (Tutorial4b).

2.5. Creating 3D heatmaps

```
Source package:
t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t1_plots.t3_heatmap3d
```

This tutorial follows a similar structurization to the already discussed tutorial on creating 2D plots (Section 2). Further, they are similar to each other to a large extent. Thus, the source codes are not presented or examined here for conciseness. The expected renders are, however, illustrated in Figure 9 (Tutorial5a) and Figure 10 (Tutorial5b).

Figure 7: Expected visualization product (Heatmap 2D; Tutorial4a)

Figure 9: Expected visualization product (Heatmap 3D; Tutorial5a)

Figure 8: Expected visualization product (Heatmap 2D; Tutorial4b)

Figure 10: Expected visualization product (Heatmap 3D; Tutorial5b)

3. Concise creation of evolutionary algorithms

This update introduces several classes that intend to allow swift designing methods for constructing initial populations, specimen evaluation, and reproduction. Specifically (*EvolutionaryComputation* module):

- *phase.DoubleConstruct*,
- *phase.IntConstruct*,

- *phase.BoolConstruct*,
- *phase.ChromosomeConstruct*,
- *phase.DoubleEvaluate*,
- *phase.IntEvaluate*,
- *phase.BoolEvaluate*,
- *phase.ChromosomeEvaluate*,

- *reproduce.DoubleReproduce*,
- *reproduce.IntReproduce*,
- *reproduce.BoolReproduce*,
- *reproduce.ChromosomeReproduce*.

The class name's prefix suggests the specimen representation type (e.g., Double = decision vector of doubles), while the suffix indicates the associated phase (or task). All these implementations make implicit assumptions regarding the designed evolutionary process. These are:

- current population, mating pool, selected parents, and the offspring are stored in their associated fields in *SpecimensContainer*,
- one offspring is generated using two parent objects.

Let us inspect the *phase.DoubleEvaluate* class (note that the other classes are structured similarly, thus do not need elaboration). The source code is brought in Listing 3 for convenience.

First, *phase.DoubleEvaluate* implements the *IEvaluate* interface, which means that it is supposed to evaluate each specimen supplied via a specimen array (*evaluateSpecimens(ArrayList<Specimen>specimens* method). This implementation, however, delegates the evaluation of each specimen to an implementation of an auxiliary *phase.DoubleEvaluate.IEvaluate* interface (inner interface). Its only method is *double [] evaluate(double [] v)*, and its implementation is assumed to return the evaluation vector given the input specimen's double decision vector. Since the inner interface is plain, the *phase.DoubleEvaluate* object can be instantiated with a concisely specified evaluation procedure that can be passed via the constructor as a lambda expression. As explained before, the "Reproduce" and "Construct" implementations follow a similar pattern and thus are not discussed here. Their examination is left to the Reader.

Listing 3: *phase.DoubleConstruct* class

```

package phase;

import exception.PhaseException;
import population.Specimen;

import java.util.ArrayList;

/**
 * A simple implementation of {@link phase.
 * IEvaluate} that delivers a convenient
 * means for evaluating specimens.
 * The specimens are assumed to be
 * evaluated based on their decision
 * double-vectors. The evaluation is
 * delegated to
 * an implementation of an auxiliary
 * IEvaluate interface.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */

```

```

15 public class DoubleEvaluate implements
    IEvaluate
{
    /**
     * Supportive interface for evaluating
     * specimens based on their decision
     * double-vectors.
     */
    public interface IEvaluate
    {
        /**
         * The main method's signature.
         *
         * @param v input decision vector (
         *         doubles)
         * @return evaluations
         */
        double[] evaluate(double[] v);
    }

    /**
     * Object responsible for evaluating
     * initial decision vectors.
     */
    private final IEvaluate _evaluator;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param evaluator object responsible
     *         for evaluating initial decision
     *         vectors
     */
    public DoubleEvaluate(IEvaluate evaluator
    )
    {
        _evaluator = evaluator;
    }

    /**
     * The method for evaluating specimens
     * based on their decision vectors (
     * doubles). The evaluation is delegated
     * to
     * an object implementing the supportive
     * {@link IEvaluate} interface.
     *
     * @param specimens array of specimens to
     *         be evaluated
     * @throws PhaseException an exception
     *         can be thrown and propagated higher
     */
    @Override
    public void evaluateSpecimens(ArrayList<
    Specimen> specimens) throws
    PhaseException
    {
        for (Specimen s : specimens) s.
            setEvaluations(_evaluator.evaluate(s
            .getDoubleDecisionVector()));
    }
}

```

Before proceeding to the tutorials' code, let us inspect a few additional classes added and changes done to existing ones in this update.

First, this update revisits the *IRandom* interface (*Utils* module) and reproduction-related interfaces and their implementations:

- *reproduction.valuecheck.IValueCheck*,
- *reproduction.operators.crossover.ICrossover*,
- *reproduction.operators.mutation.IMutate*.

Regarding *IRandom*, methods for constructing arrays of random numbers (or boolean flags) are introduced and implemented in the default *MersenneTwister64* class to facilitate random array construction. When it comes to the reproduction-related interfaces and their implementation, the return types of their primary methods are changed from void to the input type, and it is assumed that the input arrays to be processed are returned by these operators. This change allows for concise execution of operators as nested function calls.

Nonetheless, three additional classes that allow for defining the reproduction flow even more compactly are introduced:

- *reproduction.StandardDoubleReproducer*,
- *reproduction.StandardIntReproducer*,
- *reproduction.StandardBoolReproducer*,

They serve as simple wrappers for the crossover operator (*reproduction.operators.crossover.ICrossover*), the mutation operator (*reproduction.operators.mutation.IMutate*), and the object for checking whether the variable values are in their feasible bounds (*reproduction.valuecheck.IValueCheck*). They also have a simple method *reproduce* that first creates the offspring decision vector using two parents' decision vectors (inputs). The offspring is then optionally mutated, and – lastly and optionally – the feasibility of its variable values is checked. This method's signature matches the signature of the already discussed *reproduce.DoubleReproduce* (etc.) interfaces. Thus, combining these two can be done via a method reference.

Next, *phase.Sort* – a new extension of *AbstractSortPhase* is introduced. It is structured similarly to the *phase.DoubleConstruct* (etc.) classes. Specifically, its task is to sort population members stored in the specimen container (*SpecimenContainer.getPopulation()*). The sorting procedure can be explicitly passed when instantiating *phase.Sort* via its inner interface *ISort* (one-method interface).

Finally, another two simple – as for now – factory-like classes are introduced:

- *EAFactory*: facilitates creation of evolutionary algorithms,
- *DataUpdaterFactory*: facilitates creation of data updates used to update data sets maintained by the plots (*Visualization* module).

3.1. Example use cases (single-objective optimization)

Source package: *t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t2_soo*

This tutorial includes four sub-tutorials:

1. *Tutorial2aDouble*: concerns modeling solutions using an array of double values,
2. *Tutorial2bDouble*: concerns modeling solutions using an array of integer values,
3. *Tutorial2cBoolean*: concerns modeling solutions using an array of integer values,
4. *Tutorial2dChromosome*: concerns modeling solutions using three arrays: an array of doubles, an array of integers, and an array of booleans.

All these tutorials concern a trivial problem of minimizing the sum of array elements. It is assumed that, for boolean representations, *false* is mapped into 0 while *true* into 1. As for the mixed representation, the final evaluation is defined as the sum of elements of all three arrays. Regarding doubles, they are limited to [0-1] intervals, while integers are bounded by 0 from below and 10 from above. Further, the initial specimens are initialized as random arrays whose values are drawn from the uniform distribution. Since all these tutorials are similar, given the task and the code structure, this document discusses case (1) while leaving (2-4) to the Reader for inspection.

Consider Listing 4 first. It prepares some standard parameters: population size, the number of decision variables (array length), the limit for the number of generations the method should run for, the criteria (criterion) definition (cost-type), and a random number generator.

Listing 4: *Tutorial2aDouble*: defining standard parameters and objects

```
int ps = 20; // population size
int n = 10; // no. decision variables
int gens = 50; // limit for the number of
generations
Criteria criteria = Criteria.
    constructCriterion("Minimize sum", false
); // Criterion
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0); //
RGN
```

Next, Listing 5 showcases how different phases of the evolutionary algorithm can be defined. First, it creates an instance of *DoubleConstruct.IConstruct* defining the initial specimen decision vector as an array of randomly generated doubles (of size 20, note that the *IConstruct* interface's method provides the random number generator (*R1* – reference) obtained from the evolutionary method, which should be used in the construction process.

Next, the evaluation procedure – *DoubleEvaluate.IEvaluate* – is defined. The interface's method passes the specimen's decision vector (doubles) as input and expects to return an evaluation (performance) vector. In the code, this is instantiated as a

```

Generation = 0
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 15]: 2.9634396782801793; 0,59 0,09 0,01 0,07 0,56 0,72 0,12 0,12 0,28 0,41
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 5]: 3.176474750500286; 0,19 0,47 0,16 0,09 0,56 0,26 0,63 0,12 0,25 0,46
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 4]: 4.0978991188548735; 0,52 0,64 0,27 0,72 0,01 0,61 0,75 0,17 0,19 0,22
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 18]: 4.168191296527913; 0,79 0,94 0,16 0,27 0,01 0,28 0,71 0,50 0,25 0,25
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 0]: 4.171595378294331; 0,15 0,20 0,17 0,09 0,28 0,73 0,14 0,88 0,80 0,74
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 3]: 4.229626366717871; 0,62 0,80 0,23 0,80 0,05 0,00 0,30 0,66 0,49 0,26
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 12]: 4.4519259939775395; 0,86 0,19 0,32 0,33 0,58 0,46 0,68 0,96 0,01 0,05
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 19]: 4.689859792651906; 0,51 0,82 0,75 0,41 0,53 0,04 0,20 0,41 0,69 0,34
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 9]: 5.132679289443556; 0,26 0,45 0,02 0,97 0,56 0,50 0,88 0,06 0,97 0,46
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 6]: 5.187917464064825; 0,99 0,59 0,56 0,56 0,31 0,63 0,96 0,31 0,06 0,23
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 7]: 5.2467814270905295; 0,76 0,92 0,59 0,22 0,63 0,54 0,57 0,41 0,44 0,16
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 11]: 5.273244640803449; 0,45 0,13 0,77 0,12 0,94 0,92 0,37 0,38 0,80 0,39
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 17]: 5.676564812012948; 0,87 0,66 0,66 0,32 0,45 0,07 0,73 0,03 0,93 0,95
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 10]: 5.692557429101699; 0,89 0,39 0,70 0,99 0,38 0,07 0,18 0,45 0,95 0,70
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 13]: 6.2720605354779515; 0,98 0,36 0,02 0,96 0,39 0,80 0,54 0,79 0,90 0,54
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 2]: 6.328812071943775; 0,97 0,41 0,51 0,53 0,75 0,86 0,01 0,75 0,96 0,59
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 8]: 6.364916343592597; 0,57 0,73 0,59 0,30 0,29 0,57 0,85 0,88 0,73 0,86
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 1]: 6.506680444057496; 0,01 0,91 0,11 0,87 0,81 0,81 0,71 0,92 0,79 0,55
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 16]: 6.640578529790222; 0,68 0,67 0,08 0,88 0,91 0,93 0,61 0,62 0,31 0,95
[EA id = 0, generation = 0, steady-state repeat = 0, no. = 14]: 7.309628044784569; 0,72 0,76 0,68 0,41 0,93 0,98 0,32 0,70 0,95 0,87

```

Figure 11: Console output for the 0-th generation

1-element array whose only element is a sum of elements of the input decision vector (the goal in this example is to minimize such a sum).

Following, the code defines the reproduction procedure. This example showcases two ways: (1) commented out: using lambda expression executing the nested methods calls, or (2) employing *StandardDoubleReproducer* coupled with the lambda expression via method reference. Both options use the same reproduction flow. They use the SBX operator (application probability of 1.0 and the distribution index of 10.0) to construct the offspring. Then, the PM operator (application probability of 1/20 and the distribution index of 10) is applied. Finally, an auxiliary *Wrap* procedure that finally corrects those of the offspring's decision variable values that are not in the allowed bound of [0-1] is used. These operators are used when defining the reproduction scheme, i.e., the implementation of the *DoubleReproduce.IReproduce* interface. The interface's method provides, as an input, two parents' decision vectors and the random number generator.

Listing 5: *Tutorial2aDouble*: defining the procedure for specimens initialization, evaluation and reproduction

```

DoubleConstruct.IConstruct constructor = R1
-> R1.nextDoubles(n); // initial
  decision vectors: random arrays of
  doubles (size = n)
DoubleEvaluate.IEvaluate evaluator = v ->
  new double[] {StatUtils.sum(v)}; //
  evaluation function: sum of decision
  variable values

// Reproduce this way (option #1):
//SBX sbx = new SBX(1.0d, 10.0d); // SBX
  used as the crossover operator
//PM pm = new PM(1.0d / (double) n, 10.0d);
  // PM used as the crossover operator
//IValueCheck vc = new Wrap(); // value

```

```

  check for the reproducer (checks if
  variables are in [0, 1] bounds and
  conditionally corrects them)
//DoubleReproduce.IReproduce reproducer = (
  p1, p2, R1) -> // tells how an offspring
  decision vector is constructed from
  parents' vectors
//
  vc.checkAndCorrect(pm.mutate(sbx.
  crossover(p1, p2, R1), R1), 0.0d, 1.0d);

// Option #2: Instantiates the standard
  reproduced (2 parents per offspring;
  decision vectors of the same length; of
  doubles)
// 1. SBX used as the crossover operator
// 2. PM used as the crossover operator
// 3. value check for the reproducer (Wrap
  class; checks if variables are in [0, 1]
  bounds and conditionally corrects them)
StandardDoubleReproducer sdr = new
  StandardDoubleReproducer(new SBX(1.0d,
  10.0d), new PM(1.0d/(double) n, 10.0d),
  new Wrap(), 0.0d, 1.0d);
// tells how an offspring decision vector
  is constructed from parents' vectors
DoubleReproduce.IReproduce reproducer = sdr
  ::reproduce;

```

Next, the code snippet in Listing 6 finalizes the creation of the evolutionary algorithm. First, it defines the sorting phase as sorting current population members according to their performance value (first element of their performance vectors) in ascending order (it is assumed that the specimens are ordered from best to worst). Then, a random parent selection procedure is defined. Finally, the *EAFactory* class is employed to instantiate the algorithm using all already defined procedures. The instantiated method follows a basic generational scheme of the evolution and uses the default parameterization

of the phases (see `phase.PhasesBundle.getDefaultInstance()`). Naturally, the procedures defined in this tutorial are used to overwrite their corresponding phases (e.g., `evaluator` is used to instantiate `DoubleEvaluate` phase as the specimen evaluation phase; see the code of the employed `getGenerationalEA` method).

Listing 6: *Tutorial2aDouble*: finalizing creation of the evolutionary algorithm

```
// Sort in the ascending order of the first
// objective value (first elements are
// preferred; the objective function is to
// minimize the sum)
Sort sort = new SortByPerformanceValue(true
); // sort by performance (first
// objective value); ascending order

ISelect selector = new Random(); // use
// random parents selection (two parents
// per offspring)
// Create the EA using the factory object:
EA ea = EAFactory.getGenerationalEA("EA",
ps, criteria, R, constructor, evaluator,
reproducer, sort, selector);
```

The remainder of the tutorial's source code instantiates and employs `Runner` object to execute the evolutionary algorithm designed in this tutorial (the code is not brought here for conciseness). The state of the current population is logged to the console after each generation. For convenience, Figure 11 illustrates such a state in 0-th (the first) generation. Each row is associated with one population member (ordered as stored in the specimen container). Each row begins the the specimen *ID* (its string representation). Then, a performance value (the sum of the decision variables) is printed. Finally, a row ends with the decision vector string representation.

3.2. Example use cases (multi-objective optimization)

Source package: `t1_t10.t9_facilitating_usage.t3_moo`

This brief tutorial employs the major components that were presented in the previous section to define a multi-objective optimization problem, instantiate the MOEA/D algorithm, and perform the evolution along with the visualization. The problem to be solved is two-objective and straightforward:

$$\min f_1 = x_1 \cdot \left(1 + \sum_{i=2}^{20} x_i\right), \quad (1)$$

$$\min f_1 = (1 - x_1) \cdot \left(1 + \sum_{i=2}^{20} x_i\right), \quad (2)$$

$$s.t. x_1, \dots, x_{20} \in [0, 1]. \quad (3)$$

Listing 7 presents the tutorial's source code. Since it introduces nothing new, it is left to the Reader for the examination. Figure 12 portrays the expected final render for convenience.

Listing 7: *Tutorial3*

```
Criteria criteria = Criteria.
    constructCriteria("C", 2, false); //
    Criteria
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0); //
    RGN
DoubleConstruct.IConstruct constructor = R1
    -> R1.nextDoubles(20); // initial
    decision vectors: random arrays of
    doubles (size = n)
DoubleEvaluate.IEvaluate evaluator = v ->
    new double[]{v[0] * (1.0d + MathUtils.
    getSum(v, 1, 19)), (1.0d - v[0]) * (1.0d
    + MathUtils.getSum(v, 1, 19))}; //
    evaluation function: sum of decision
    variable values
StandardDoubleReproducer sdr = new
    StandardDoubleReproducer(new SBX(1.0d,
    30.0d), new PM(1.0d/(double) 20, 30.0d),
    new Wrap(), 0.0d, 1.0d);
DoubleReproduce.IReproduce reproducer = sdr
    ::reproduce; // instantiates reproducer
IGoal[] goals = GoalsFactory.getPBIsDND(2,
    19, 5.0d); // instantiates goals
MOEAD moead = MOEAD.getMOEAD(R, goals,
    criteria, constructor, evaluator,
    reproducer, new Euclidean(), 5); //
    instantiates MOEAD

try
{
    // Creates standard 2D plot and the frame
    :
    Plot2D plot2D = Plot2DFactory.getPlot("f1
    ", "f2", 1.0f, 1.5f, scheme -> scheme.
    _colors.put(ColorFields.
    PLOT_BACKGROUND, color.Color.WHITE),
    null);
    Frame frame = new Frame(plot2D, 0.5f);
    // Creates standard data updater:
    DataUpdater du = DataUpdaterFactory.
    getSimpleDataUpdater(frame.getModel().
    getPlotsWrapper(), new EASource(moead)
    , DSFactory2D.getReferenceDS("MOEAD",
    new MarkerStyle(2.0f, Color.RED,
    Marker.CIRCLE)));
    // Creates the visualization object and
    the runner:
    IVisualization visualization = new
    Visualization(frame, du);
    Runner runner = new Runner(new Runner.
    Params(moead, 20, visualization));
    // Executes the evolution:
    runner.executeEvolution(500);
} catch (Exception e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}
```


Figure 12: Expected final render